

Exploring glycan binding by *Fusobacterium nucleatum* Fap2 adhesin for applications in cancer research

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Mucin-type O-glycosylation of cell-surface and secreted proteins is associated with cell development and differentiation. Alterations of O-glycosylation also modulate aggressive colorectal cancer (CRC) phenotypes, and tumor associated O-glycans are crucial molecular targets for therapy and as clinical biomarkers. Research on the human microbiome uncovered that dysbiosis with an unbalanced abundance of *Fusobacterium nucleatum* leads to a pro-inflammatory milieu, promoting tumor growth¹. Evidence shows the role of recognition of tumor-expressed glycans by the *F. nucleatum* adhesin Fap2 in mediating signalling in CRC. Still, it is unknown how CRC-associated glycans are differentially recognised by Fap2 adhesin. In this communication, we will present initial results aiming at the characterization of Fap2 glycan-binding specificity, combining protein structural analysis and human O-glycome microarrays. Ultimately, the goal is to elucidate how O-glycans are exploited by bacteria at a molecular level and identify protein targets to modulate bacterial adhesion to cancer cell models. Through bioinformatic sequence and structural analysis of Fap2 adhesin, several Fap2 fragments spanning the entire Fap2 extracellular domain were designed and expressed as recombinant proteins. Initial data showed structured and functional Fap2 fragments with interaction to terminal galactosylated glycoproteins, and sialylation inhibiting the binding.

References

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